

ANALYSIS OF TUBERCULOSIS RELAPSES IN TASHKENT CLINIC HOSPITAL

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Introduction. Tuberculosis remains one of the most significant infectious diseases with a pronounced social component. Despite advances in diagnostics and treatment, disease relapse continues to pose a serious challenge to clinicians and public health systems. The recurrence of tuberculosis significantly worsens the prognosis, increases the risk of complications, and raises the epidemiological threat. Identifying and analyzing factors associated with relapse is essential to improving prevention and treatment strategies.

Objective. To examine the frequency, clinical features, and key predisposing factors of tuberculosis relapses, as well as their correlation with patients' socio-demographic characteristics.

Materials and Methods. A retrospective analysis was conducted on 64 medical records of patients treated for pulmonary tuberculosis relapse from 2022 to 2024. Clinical, radiological, laboratory, and anamnesis data were assessed. Factors analyzed included gender, age, social status, substance use, HIV status, and seasonal distribution of relapses.

Results/ Gender and Age: The majority of patients were male - 58 (90,6%), while 6 (9,4%) were female. The highest relapse frequency was observed among men aged 30–39 years - 27 cases (42.2% of males). A similar trend was noted among women, with five cases in the same age group.

Social and Behavioral Factors: Over half of the patients had no stable income. Notable risk factors included: Alcohol abuse: 51 patients (79.7%), "Drug use was reported in 5 patients (7.8%)," "HIV-positive status was noted in 6 patients (9.4%)," Homelessness - 3 (4.7%).

Clinical Forms: Fibrocavernous tuberculosis - 39 cases (59.5%), Infiltrative tuberculosis with destruction - 24 cases (39.2%), "Cavernous tuberculosis in the dissemination phase: 1 case"

Seasonal Distribution: Spring — 22 cases (33.4%), Autumn — 22 (37.5%), Winter — 12 (18.8%), Summer — 6 (9.4%).

Discussion. The findings indicate a high prevalence of severe forms of tuberculosis in relapse cases, likely due to delayed healthcare-seeking behavior, non-compliance with previous treatment, and the impact of adverse social factors. The most vulnerable group consisted of socially disadvantaged men of working age. The predominance of fibrocavernous and infiltrative forms reflects a trend toward chronic disease progression. Seasonal peaks in spring and autumn may be associated with fluctuations in immune function and environmental conditions.

Conclusion.

1. Tuberculosis relapse is more frequent among socially vulnerable males aged 30–39 years.
2. Major predisposing factors include alcohol abuse, lack of stable living conditions, and HIV infection.
3. Fibrocavernous and infiltrative forms are most common in relapses, indicating severe disease progression.
4. Seasonal analysis revealed higher incidence in spring and autumn.

Effective prevention of tuberculosis relapses requires a multidisciplinary approach, combining medical treatment with social and behavioral interventions.